

The Mediating Role of Innovation Climate in the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employees' Sustainable Performance*

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Abstract

Keywords:

Job Satisfaction,
Innovation
Climate,
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Behavior

This study investigates the mediating role of innovation climate in the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance. The theoretical foundations are based on Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964) and the Positive Organizational Behavior approach (Luthans, 2002). Although recent studies have increasingly explored the interaction among job satisfaction, innovation climate, and individual sustainable performance, few have examined these three variables within a single, integrative model. Addressing this gap, the study analyzes data collected from 411 healthcare employees in Türkiye using a quantitative survey design. Job satisfaction was measured with the short form of Brayfield & Rothe, innovation climate with Scott & Bruce's scale, and sustainable performance with Ji, De Jonge, Peeters & Taris's instrument. Structural validity was tested through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), while hypotheses were examined using Baron and Kenny's (1986) mediation approach via PROCESS Macro Model 4 (Hayes, 2018) with 5,000 bootstrap samples and 95% confidence intervals. Findings reveal that the innovation climate partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance. In other words, job satisfaction enhances sustainable performance both directly and indirectly through an innovation-supportive organizational atmosphere. The empirical results confirm the proposed theoretical relationships and demonstrate that innovation climate functions as a critical intermediary mechanism between job satisfaction and sustainable performance. Overall, the findings suggest that employee satisfaction and innovation climate should be regarded not merely as "good management practices," but as strategic organizational resources essential for sustaining long-term employee performance.

İş Tatmininin Çalışanın Sürdürülebilir Performansı Üzerindeki Etkisinde Yenilik İkliminin Aracılık Rolü

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

İş Tatmini,
Yenilik İklimi,
Sürdürülebilir
Performans,
Sosyal Değişim
Teorisi,
Pozitif Örgütsel
Davranış

Bu çalışma, iş tatmininin çalışanın sürdürülebilir performansı üzerindeki etkisinde yenilik ikliminin aracılık rolünü incelemektedir. Araştırmanın teorik temelleri Sosyal Değişim Teorisi (Blau, 1964) ve Pozitif Örgütsel Davranış yaklaşımına (Luthans, 2002) dayanmaktadır. Son yıllarda iş tatmini, yenilik iklimi ve bireysel sürdürülebilir performans etkileşimini irdeleyen çalışmalar artsa da, bu üç değişkeni aynı modelde bütüncül biçimde ele alan ampirik araştırmalar sınırlıdır. Bu çalışma, söz konusu boşluğu kapatmak üzere, Türkiye'de farklı illerde görev yapan 411 sağlık çalışanından anket yöntemiyle toplanan verileri analiz etmektedir. Ölçümler Brayfield & Rothe kısa formu (iş tatmini), Scott & Bruce (yenilik iklimi) ve Ji, De Jonge, Peeters & Taris (sürdürülebilir performans) ölçekleriyle yapılmıştır. Yapısal geçerlik Doğrulayıcı Faktör Analizi (DFA) ile test edilmiş; hipotezler Baron & Kenny yaklaşımı temel alınarak PROCESS Macro Model 4 (Hayes) ile sınanmış, bootstrap=5000 ve %95 güven aralığı kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, yenilik ikliminin iş tatmini ile sürdürülebilir performans arasındaki ilişkide kısmi aracılık üstlendiğini göstermektedir. Başka bir ifadeyle, iş tatmini sürdürülebilir performansı hem doğrudan hem de yeniliği destekleyen örgütsel atmosfer üzerinden dolaylı olarak güçlendirmektedir. Sonuçlar, çalışmanın kuramsal çerçevesinde öngörülen ilişkilerin ampirik olarak doğrulandığını ve yenilik ikliminin bu etkileşimde kritik bir ara mekanizma işlevi gördüğünü ortaya koymaktadır. Sonuç olarak, çalışan memnuniyeti ve yenilik iklimi yalnızca "iyi yönetim uygulamaları" değil, performansın sürdürülebilirliğini mümkün kılan stratejik kaynaklar olarak değerlendirilebilir.

* This study is derived from the first author's master's thesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important ways to achieve sustainable competitive advantage in today's organizations is to ensure the continuity of employee performance. The sustainability of individual performance is not only about an employee's ability to fulfill current job responsibilities, but also about maintaining motivation, productivity, and innovative potential over the long term. In this context, sustaining employee performance has become one of the key strategic objectives of organizations (Afsar, 2019).

Job satisfaction refers to employees' positive emotional attitudes toward their work and their overall satisfaction derived from experiences within the organization. This concept is an important psychological variable that directly influences individuals' perceptions of work, value judgments, and organizational commitment (Locke, 1976). Herzberg's (1959) Two-Factor Theory explains job satisfaction through motivating and hygiene factors, and since then, numerous studies have consistently emphasized its impact on employee performance. The meta-analysis conducted by Judge, Thoresen, Bono, and Patton (2001) revealed a significant and positive relationship between job satisfaction and performance. Similarly, Kim and Park (2019) stated that satisfied employees contribute more to their organizations and are more willing to maintain their performance. However, the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance cannot be explained solely by individual attitudes. It is also shaped by factors such as an organization's openness to innovation, learning capacity, and the psychological safety climate it provides for employees. At this point, the innovation climate represents an organizational atmosphere in which employees are encouraged to generate new ideas, take risks, and contribute to change (Amabile, Conti, Coon, Lazenby & Herron, 1996). An innovative climate allows satisfied employees to channel their energy into creative outputs and sustain their performance in the long term (Anderson et al., 2014; Shanker et al., 2017). Therefore, the innovation climate may play a mediating role in the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance (Scott & Bruce, 1994).

The theoretical foundations of this study are based on Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964) and the Positive Organizational Behavior approach (Luthans, 2002). According to Social Exchange Theory, employees reciprocate the support and favorable treatment they receive from their organizations by exhibiting higher levels of effort and performance. This perspective explains how job satisfaction contributes to sustainable performance by fostering a sense of reciprocity-driven motivation among employees. Similarly, the Positive Organizational Behavior approach posits that employees' psychological resources are key determinants of performance sustainability. These psychological resources including self-efficacy, competence, hope, psychological capital, resilience, and optimism have significant effects on work outcomes and performance (Luthans & Youssef, 2007). Job satisfaction, as a result of these resources, facilitates employees' engagement in innovative behaviors and supports the maintenance of long-term performance.

In recent years, studies have increasingly examined the interaction between job satisfaction, innovation climate, and individual sustainable performance within organizations. However, research that integrates these three variables into a single, comprehensive model remains quite limited. This study aims to fill this gap by empirically testing the mediating role of innovation climate in the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Job satisfaction is a fundamental organizational behavior variable that reflects an individual's overall level of contentment with their job, as well as their emotional evaluation of the work environment and assigned tasks. Employees' job satisfaction leads to numerous positive outcomes such as organizational commitment, motivation, and enhanced performance. Locke (1976) defined job satisfaction as a positive emotional state resulting from an individual's evaluation of their job or job experiences. High levels of job satisfaction directly influence both employees' behaviors within the organization and their long-term performance. According to Herzberg's (1959) Two-Factor Theory, motivating factors such as recognition, responsibility, achievement, the nature of the work itself, opportunities for growth and advancement, and feedback enhance job satisfaction, while hygiene factors including pay, working conditions, job security, personal life, supervision style, company policies, status, and interpersonal relations serve to prevent dissatisfaction.

The innovation climate refers to an organizational environment in which employees are encouraged to generate new ideas, develop creative solutions, and actively participate in change processes. This type of climate not only

enhances an organization's capacity to adapt to change but also positively influences employees' motivation and job satisfaction levels.

In this context, an innovation climate can foster organizational learning by creating an atmosphere where employees feel safe to share ideas without fear of making mistakes. Such an environment may facilitate the transformation of employees' job satisfaction into sustainable performance behaviors. Shanker et al. (2017) found that when an innovation climate is combined with job satisfaction, it produces a significant positive effect on individual performance.

Sustainable performance refers to an employee's ability to maintain productivity, motivation, and work quality over the long term. At its core, sustainable performance is grounded in psychological resilience, a willingness to learn, and organizational support. In this context, an individual's capacity to sustain long-term efficiency is nourished by both internal and external resources. Job satisfaction, as a positive emotional state arising from one's experiences within the organization, represents one of the most crucial of these resources. Employees with high job satisfaction tend to maintain their performance more consistently due to their sense of belonging and motivation toward the organization (Abdelhamied et al., 2023). On the other hand, an innovation climate provides a supportive environment at the organizational level that facilitates the continuity of sustainable performance. Therefore, sustainable performance develops not only through individual resilience but also through the emotional energy provided by job satisfaction and the organizational encouragement fostered by an innovation climate. In this regard, job satisfaction and innovation climate can be considered two fundamental antecedents of sustainable performance.

Theoretically, these relationships can be explained through Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964) and the Positive Organizational Behavior approach (Luthans, 2002). According to Social Exchange Theory, employees demonstrate greater effort, commitment, and performance in response to the support and favorable conditions they receive from their organization. Job satisfaction represents one of the key indicators of this reciprocal relationship between the employee and the organization. The Positive Organizational Behavior approach, on the other hand, posits that employees' psychological resources such as efficacy, hope, psychological capital, resilience, and optimism enhance and sustain job performance (Luthans & Youssef, 2007).

In this context, job satisfaction activates individuals' internal resources, while the innovation climate provides the organizational foundation that enables these resources to transform into behavioral outcomes. Therefore, when job satisfaction and innovation climate are considered together, employees' sustainable performance levels are expected to increase. Based on this framework, the proposed research model suggests that the innovation climate plays a mediating role in the effect of job satisfaction on employees' sustainable performance.

In recent years, studies have increasingly examined the interaction between job satisfaction, innovation climate, and individual sustainable performance within organizations. Although some research has found that job satisfaction does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance (Tirtayasa, Nurhayati, Sari & Syahri, 2025), the majority of studies in the literature indicate a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and individual performance (Shanker et al., 2017; Anderson et al., 2014; Berman et al., 2021; Robbins & Judge, 2023; Muafi et al., 2023; Abdelhamied et al., 2023; Demircioğlu, 2025; Quan & Khan, 2025; Lukito et al., 2025). For example, Muafi et al. (2023) found that job satisfaction positively influences both sustainable and overall job performance among SME entrepreneurs. Similarly, Quan and Khan (2025) revealed that implementing quality management practices enhances job satisfaction, strengthens competitive advantage, and promotes sustainable performance. Abdelhamied et al. (2023) also reported that job satisfaction significantly contributes to operational performance, which is considered a component of sustainable performance. Furthermore, Lukito et al. (2025) identified job satisfaction as the strongest determinant of sustainable employee performance. These findings are consistent with the perspectives of Robbins and Judge (2023) and Berman et al. (2021), who argue that job satisfaction manifests through more productive, committed employees who are more likely to remain within the organization in the long term.

In the literature, the relationship between innovation climate and job satisfaction has generally been examined through correlation analyses (Johnson & McIntyre, 1998; Kaya et al., 2010). These studies are significant for understanding how an innovative organizational climate influences employee attitudes. Scott and Bruce (1994) and Shanker et al. (2017) found that an innovation climate strengthens employees' creativity and individual performance. Similarly, Lee et al. (2014) and Demircioğlu (2025) demonstrated that the innovation climate has a direct positive effect on job satisfaction. However, most previous studies have focused on the effects of

innovation climate as an outcome variable on performance or job satisfaction. Conversely, some research has shown that satisfied employees also contribute to strengthening the innovation climate, indicating a reciprocal relationship between these two variables (Sun et al., 2024; Weston, 2009; Abukhait & Pillai, 2017; Ren et al., 2021). These findings suggest that job satisfaction is not merely an outcome but also a key antecedent that fosters organizational innovation. According to Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), when managers provide a fair, supportive, and satisfying work environment, employees reciprocate through increased organizational commitment and innovative behaviors (Urhan et al., 2021). Therefore, employees with higher job satisfaction are more likely to make meaningful contributions to promoting and sustaining organizational innovation (Emiralioğlu & Sönmez, 2021). Moreover, empirical evidence indicates that innovation climate functions as an essential organizational factor that enhances employees' creativity, innovative behavior, and job performance. You et al. (2022) found that employees with a high perception of innovation climate exhibit stronger innovative work performance. Similarly, Jiang (2023), in a cross-country study conducted in the service sector, revealed that individuals with higher perceptions of an innovative climate demonstrate significantly greater motivation and performance. These findings indicate that an innovation climate not only promotes creative behavior but also positively influences employees' ability to maintain long-term productivity and work quality.

In conclusion, empirical studies that comprehensively examine job satisfaction, innovation climate, and sustainable employee performance within a single model remain quite limited in the existing literature. This study aims to fill this gap by empirically testing the mediating role of innovation climate in the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance. In doing so, the research seeks to contribute to the understanding of human-centered and innovation-based organizational dynamics that support sustainable success in organizations.

Based on this theoretical foundation, the following hypotheses were developed:

H₁: *Job satisfaction positively affects employees' sustainable performance.*

H₂: *Job satisfaction positively affects innovation climate.*

H₃: *Innovation climate positively affects employees' sustainable performance.*

H₄: *Innovation climate mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance.*

To test the validity of the proposed model, a quantitative research design was adopted, and the relationships among the variables were statistically analyzed.

3. METHOD

This research is a quantitative study that examines the effect of job satisfaction on employees' sustainable performance and the mediating role of innovation climate in this relationship. The study was designed within the framework of a correlational research model, aiming to statistically test the causal relationships among the variables.

The population of this research consists of healthcare employees working in Türkiye. To enhance the feasibility of the study in terms of time and cost, a convenience sampling method was employed. Accordingly, healthcare professionals working in both public and private hospitals across different provinces were reached. The sample size was determined with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Once the minimum required sample size was achieved, the data collection process was concluded. In total, 411 healthcare employees participated in the survey. Due to the nature of the study, participants were drawn from different institutions and job levels, which enhances the generalizability of the findings. Accordingly, demographic variables such as age, gender, professional experience, position, and education level of the participants were also included in the analyses as control variables.

The data collection instrument consists of four sections. The first section includes the demographic characteristics of the participants, while the remaining three sections contain the scales related to the main variables of the study. In the second section, to measure the general job satisfaction levels of healthcare employees, the unidimensional "Job Satisfaction Scale" developed by Brayfield and Rothe (1951), shortened to a five-item version by Judge, Locke, Durham, and Kluger (1998), and adapted into Turkish by Keser and Bilir (2019) was used. In the third section, the "Innovation Climate Scale" developed by Scott and Bruce (1994) and adapted into Turkish by Sönmez, Bacaksız, and Yıldırım (2017), consisting of 14 items, was employed to assess healthcare employees' perceptions of the innovation climate. In the fourth section, the "Sustainable Employee

Performance Scale” developed by Ji, De Jonge, Peeters, and Taris (2021) and adapted into Turkish by Çilhoroz, Topaktaş, and Işık (2023), consisting of 10 unidimensional items, was used to measure sustainable performance levels of healthcare employees. The scale evaluates an individual’s tendency to maintain productivity, work motivation, and performance continuity over the long term. Participants responded to all scale items using a five-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree).

The data were collected through both online (Google Forms) and printed questionnaires. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. The collected data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics 23.0, Hayes PROCESS Macro v4.2, and AMOS 21 software. After checking for missing and outlier values, the normality assumption was tested using skewness and kurtosis values. The fact that skewness and kurtosis values were within the ± 1 range supported the assumption of normal distribution. Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients were calculated to assess the reliability of the scales, and all scales demonstrated high internal consistency with $\alpha > 0.90$ (Yıldız & Uzunsakal, 2018).

Construct validity was tested through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The hypotheses of the research model were examined based on the method proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986) and analyzed using mediation analysis via PROCESS Macro Model 4 (Hayes, 2018). The bootstrap method with 5,000 resamples was employed, and confidence intervals were set at 95%.

4. FINDINGS

The demographic data related to the sample reveal the distribution of participants across various variables. These findings not only demonstrate the diversity and representativeness of the sample but also provide a foundational reference for evaluating the relationships among the variables examined in the study. The frequency and percentage distributions of participants’ demographic characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Factors

Variable	Frequency	%	Variable	Frequency	%
Gender			Tenure (Curr. Work)		
Female	246	59,9	Less than 1 year	47	11,4
Male	165	40,1	1-5 years	180	43,8
Marital Status			6-10 years	88	21,4
Married	194	47,2	11-15 years	40	9,7
Single	217	52,8	16 years and above	56	13,6
Age Group			Position in the Workplace		
18-25	84	20,4	Doctor	106	25,8
26-33	148	36,0	Nurse/Midwife	153	37,2
34-41	107	26,0	Health Officer	81	19,7
42-49	47	11,4	Other	71	17,3
50 ve üzeri	25	6,1			
Education Level					
High School	21	5,1			
Associate Degree	50	12,2			
Bachelor’s Degree	207	50,4			
Master’s Degree	60	14,6			
Doctorate	73	17,8			

The demographic data presented in the table reveal a multifaceted profile of the healthcare professionals participating in the study. In terms of gender distribution, 59.9% of the participants are female and 40.1% are male. Regarding marital status, 52.8% of the respondents are single, while 47.2% are married. The relatively higher proportion of single participants suggests that the sample largely consists of younger age groups. Examining the age distribution, the largest group falls within the 26–33 age range (36%), followed by those aged 34–41 (26%). This indicates that the sample is predominantly composed of young and middle-aged employees. In terms of education level, more than half of the participants (50.4%) hold a bachelor’s degree, while 14.6% have a master’s degree and 17.8% hold a doctorate. These figures suggest that the sample

represents a highly educated workforce. With respect to tenure, 43.8% of the respondents have been working at their current institutions for 1–5 years, indicating a predominance of employees with moderate professional experience. An analysis of job positions shows that 37.2% of the participants are nurses or midwives, 25.8% are doctors, 19.7% are health officers, and 17.3% are in other positions. This distribution demonstrates that the sample effectively represents various professional groups within the healthcare sector.

Overall, it can be concluded that the majority of participants are female healthcare professionals who are young or middle-aged, hold a bachelor’s degree, and have between one and five years of work experience. This demographic profile indicates that the sample provides an appropriate and representative basis for evaluating variables such as innovation climate and sustainable performance within the context of this research.

The selection of statistical analysis methods in quantitative research depends on the distributional characteristics of the data. In particular, the application of parametric tests (such as t-tests, ANOVA, and regression) requires that the data approximate a normal distribution. Therefore, a normality test is conducted before performing such analyses. In this study, the normality of the dataset was first assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test ($n > 50$). The results indicated that the p-values obtained were below 0.05. However, since relying solely on p-values can be insufficient, skewness and kurtosis coefficients were also examined (George & Mallery, 2010). According to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013), skewness and kurtosis values between -1.5 and $+1.5$ indicate that the data meet the assumption of normal distribution (Table 2).

Table 2. Normality Test

Variable/ Scale	Kolmogorov–Smirnov (p)	Skewness	Kurtosis	Normality Suitability
Job Satisfaction	0.000	–0.457	–1.030	Suitable (within ± 1.5 range)
Innovation Climate	0.000	0.176	–0.982	Suitable (within ± 1.5 range)
Sustainable Employee Performance	0.000	–0.745	–0.457	Suitable (within ± 1.5 range)

According to the results presented in Table 2, the data distribution was found to be suitable for the parametric tests (correlation, regression, and mediation analyses) to be conducted in the subsequent stages of the research.

To test the construct validity of the scales, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted. Before the analysis, the adequacy of the sample size was evaluated using the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s test of sphericity. When the KMO value is below 0.50, it is generally advised not to proceed with factor analysis. Values between 0.70–0.80 indicate a good level of adequacy, 0.80–0.90 indicate a very good level, and values above 0.90 are considered excellent (Hutcheson & Sofroniou, 1999; Seçer, 2013; Çokluk, Şekercioğlu & Büyüköztürk, 2011). The analysis results are summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Explained Variance, KMO, and Validity Values

Variable/Scale	Explained Variance (%)	KMO	Bartlett’s Significance (p)	Validity Status
Job Satisfaction	80,13	0,855	0.000	Valid and strong structure
Innovation Climate	74,74	0,949	0.000	High level of validity
Sustainable Employee Perf.	79,00	0,971	0.000	Excellent level of validity

The results presented in Table 3 indicate that the scales used in the study are suitable for factor analysis and demonstrate strong construct validity. To verify the measurement structure of each scale, a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted.

Table 4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results

Job Satisfaction	Comp.	Innovation Climate	Comp.	Sust. Employee Perf.	Comp.
JS1	,923	IC1	,887	SEP1	,905
JS2	,934	IC2	,873	SEP2	,911
JS3	,878	IC3	,900	SEP3	,926
JS4	,904	IC4	,875	SEP4	,581
JS5	,833	IC5	,878	SEP5	,918
		IC6	-,704	SEP6	,927
		IC7	-,836	SEP7	,873
		IC8	-,818	SEP8	,934
		IC9	-,818	SEP9	,929
		IC10	-,735	SEP10	,924
		IC11	-,729		
		IC12	,746		
		IC13	,716		
		IC14	,682		

The Job Satisfaction Scale exhibited a single-factor structure, with all factor loadings ranging between 0.833 and 0.934. This indicates a high level of internal consistency and confirms the unidimensional nature of the scale. The Innovation Climate Scale demonstrated a predominantly multidimensional structure, as most factor loadings exceeded 0.70, providing strong support for its construct validity. The negatively loaded items represent reverse-coded statements, which yielded results in the expected direction. For the Sustainable Employee Performance Scale, factor loadings ranged from 0.581 to 0.934. Particularly, the loadings above 0.90 indicate that the unidimensional structure of the scale is strongly confirmed. The scale thus shows high validity in measuring employees' long-term commitment, competence, and continuity of performance.

When Tables 3 and 4 are evaluated together, it can be concluded that all the scales used in the study are valid and reliable in terms of both statistical adequacy (KMO, Bartlett, and explained variance) and factor structure (high factor loadings and significant components). Overall, the findings indicate that the measurement instruments used in the study demonstrate strong construct validity, sufficient sample adequacy, and are suitable for subsequent parametric analyses.

Descriptive statistics, Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients, and correlation analyses were conducted to determine the general tendencies of the variables used in the study, assess the internal consistency levels of the scales, and identify the direction and strength of the relationships among the variables. These analyses provide preliminary evidence regarding the reliability of the measurement instruments and the fundamental associations among the variables, serving as a foundation for testing the structural model. The corresponding results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics, Reliability, and Correlation Coefficients

Variables	M/SD	α	Correlations		
			JS	IC	SEP
JS	2.46/0.94	,937	-		
IC	3.42/1.14	,956	.462**	-	
SEP	3.69/1.24	,960	.548**	.345**	-

JS: Job Satisfaction, IC: Innovation Climate, SEP: Sustainable Employee Performance, M/SD. = Mean / Standard Deviation, α = Cronbach Alpha, **p < 0.01

The results of the correlation analysis indicate that there are significant and positive relationships among the variables included in the study ($p < 0.01$). The correlation coefficient between job satisfaction and innovation climate ($r = 0.462$) represents a moderate positive relationship, suggesting that as employees' job satisfaction increases, organizational support for innovative practices also rises. The relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance ($r = 0.548$) is a moderate-to-high positive correlation, indicating that employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to sustain their performance more effectively over the long term.

Meanwhile, the correlation between innovation climate and sustainable performance ($r = 0.345$) is a weak-to-moderate positive relationship, showing that an innovative work environment supports employees' continuous productivity and motivation. Based on these findings, the relationships identified are consistent with the directions of hypotheses H₁ ("Job satisfaction positively affects employees' sustainable performance"), H₂ ("Job satisfaction positively affects innovation climate"), and H₃ ("Innovation climate positively affects employees' sustainable performance"), all of which were subsequently tested through regression and mediation analyses. The results demonstrate that employees' job satisfaction not only contributes to the development of an innovative organizational climate but also strengthens their long-term performance. Moreover, the innovation climate appears to play a complementary role in maintaining employees' motivation and productivity. These findings empirically confirm the theoretically proposed direct relationships and support the overall structure of the research model.

The direct relationships among the variables were tested using multiple regression analyses, which also formed the foundation for the mediation model. Since the direct effects between job satisfaction, innovation climate, and employees' sustainable performance were assessed within the framework of Hayes' PROCESS Model 4 approach, the regression findings are presented together as part of the mediation analysis (Table 6).

Table 6. Regression Analysis Results for the Mediation Test

Predictor Variables	Dependent Variables						
	M (Innovation Climate)			Y (Sustainable Employee Performance)			
		B	S.E.		B	S.E.	
X (Job Satisfaction)	a	.489***	.046	c ¹	1,291***	.121	
M (Innovation Climate)	-	-	-	B	.287*	.114	
Constant	I _M	1,324***	.143	I _Y	-1,062**	.364	
		R ² =.213			R ² =.311		
		F(1;409) = 110,975; p<.001			F(2;408) =91,978; p<.001		

*p<.05; **p<.01; ***p<.001; R² = Explained Variance; S.H.= Standard Error; GA: Confidence Interval; b= Unstandardized Beta

According to the PROCESS analysis results presented in Table 6, job satisfaction has a significant and positive effect on innovation climate ($b = .489$; 95% CI [.398–.581]; $t = 10.534$; $p < .001$). Job satisfaction explains approximately 21% of the variance in innovation climate ($R^2 = .213$). This finding supports Hypothesis H₂ ("Job satisfaction positively affects innovation climate"). Furthermore, innovation climate has a significant and positive effect on sustainable employee performance ($b = .287$; 95% CI [.062–.512]; $t = 2.509$; $p < .05$), confirming Hypothesis H₃ ("Innovation climate positively affects employees' sustainable performance"). In addition, job satisfaction also has a direct, significant, and positive effect on sustainable employee performance ($b = 1.291$; 95% CI [1.053–1.529]; $t = 10.662$; $p < .001$), supporting Hypothesis H₁ ("Job satisfaction positively affects employees' sustainable performance").

These results indicate that innovation climate plays a partial mediating role in the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance. In other words, employees who are satisfied with their jobs are more likely to sustain their long-term performance through the perception of an innovative organizational climate. When both job satisfaction and innovation climate are included in the model, they jointly explain 31% of the variance in sustainable employee performance ($R^2 = .311$). These findings support Hypothesis H₄ ("Innovation climate mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' sustainable performance") and demonstrate that innovation climate functions as a partial mediator in this relationship. The mediation model illustrating this result is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Mediating Role of Innovation Climate in the Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Sustainable Employee Performance

The structural representation of the regression model presented in Figure 1 supports the analytical findings. As shown in the model, job satisfaction directly affects employees' sustainable performance, while this effect also occurs indirectly through the partial mediation of innovation climate. Accordingly, as employees' job satisfaction increases, the perception of an innovative organizational climate strengthens, which in turn contributes to sustaining long-term performance. The overall evaluation of the model indicates that the hypothesized relationships within the theoretical framework were empirically confirmed, demonstrating that innovation climate functions as a critical mediating mechanism between job satisfaction and sustainable performance.

The findings reveal that the relationships proposed in the model are both statistically and theoretically significant. Accordingly, the key results of the study and their consistency with the existing literature are discussed in detail in the following section.

5. RESULTS, DISCUSSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of job satisfaction on employees' sustainable performance and the mediating role of innovation climate in this relationship. Based on data collected from 411 healthcare employees across various provinces in Türkiye, the findings revealed that the relationships proposed in the research model were supported both statistically and theoretically.

First, a positive and significant relationship was found between job satisfaction and sustainable performance. As job satisfaction increased, employees' tendency to maintain their performance over the long term also strengthened ($b = 1.291$; $p < .001$). This finding indicates that employees' satisfaction with their work is related not only to immediate performance outcomes but also to the sustainability of their performance. This result is consistent with the majority of previous studies addressing this relationship (Shanker et al., 2017; Anderson et al., 2014; Berman et al., 2021; Robbins & Judge, 2023; Muafi et al., 2023; Abdelhamied et al., 2023; Demircioğlu, 2025; Quan & Khan, 2025; Lukito et al., 2025).

Second, job satisfaction was found to have a significant effect on innovation climate ($b = .489$; $p < .001$). Employees who are satisfied with their jobs perceive a stronger organizational climate that supports creativity, encourages change, and provides resources. This suggests that job satisfaction shapes not only individual attitudes but also organizational perceptions. Previous research has similarly supported this argument (Sun et al., 2024; Weston, 2009; Abukhait & Pillai, 2017; Ren et al., 2021).

Third, innovation climate was found to have a positive and significant effect on sustainable performance ($b = .287$; $p < .05$). An organizational atmosphere that supports innovation helps employees maintain motivation, organize their tasks efficiently, and uphold performance standards in the long term. This finding is in line with prior studies on this topic (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Shanker et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2024; Weston, 2009; Abukhait & Pillai, 2017; Ren et al., 2021; You et al., 2022; Jiang, 2023).

Most importantly, mediation analysis results showed that innovation climate partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance. This indicates that job satisfaction influences employees' sustainable performance both directly and indirectly by fostering an innovative, supportive, and psychologically safe work climate. When job satisfaction and innovation climate were included in the model together, 31% of the variance in sustainable performance was explained ($R^2 = .311$), supporting the overall explanatory power of the model. This study contributes to the literature as one of the first to empirically test this partial mediation effect, demonstrating that innovation climate plays a significant intermediary role in the link between job satisfaction and sustainable performance.

The obtained results provide an opportunity to reinterpret the long-debated "employee satisfaction–performance relationship" (Judge et al., 2001) in the organizational behavior and human resource management literature from a contemporary perspective. In the classical approach, job satisfaction is defined as employees' positive emotional evaluation of their work and is directly associated with performance (Locke, 1976). The contribution of this study lies in demonstrating that this relationship extends beyond immediate outcomes to sustainable performance, that is, the employee's capacity to remain productive over time. In other words, a satisfied employee does not only "perform well" but "consistently performs well."

The findings also support Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964). According to this theory, employees exhibit greater effort, commitment, and performance in response to the positive treatment they receive from their organization. Within this framework, job satisfaction can be viewed as a psychological state through which employees establish a positive cycle of reciprocity with their organization. The study's findings align with this logic, suggesting that satisfied employees enhance their sustainable performance as part of this exchange mechanism. As employees become more satisfied with their work, they tend to feel indebted to their organization, take on greater responsibility, manage their time more effectively, and maintain their performance consistently over the long term.

The second theoretical foundation of this study, the Positive Organizational Behavior approach (Luthans & Youssef, 2007), is also consistent with the findings. This approach argues that employees' psychological capital plays a critical role in sustaining job outcomes. The results position job satisfaction not merely as an emotional state of contentment but as a psychological resource that strengthens employees' self-efficacy and resilience perceptions. Highly satisfied employees perceive themselves as more competent, effective, and resilient within the organization, which in turn contributes positively to their sustainable performance.

The unique contribution of this study lies in the statistical confirmation of the mediating role of innovation climate. Previous research has provided strong evidence that innovation climate enhances creativity, proactive behavior, and individual performance (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Shanker et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2024; Weston, 2009; Abukhait & Pillai, 2017; Ren et al., 2021; You et al., 2022; Jiang, 2023). This study extends these findings by demonstrating this effect from a sustainable performance perspective. An innovative climate not only encourages employees to make one-time creative contributions but also supports the transformation of these contributions into a sustained performance regime over time. This process is particularly crucial for healthcare employees, a group often exposed to high pressure, intense workloads, and critical decision-making conditions. In such a context, maintaining performance implies not just technical competence but also the ability to continue functioning effectively without burnout. The findings suggest that enhancing job satisfaction and strengthening the innovation climate within healthcare institutions may be directly linked to the quality of patient care. This, in turn, connects organizational outcomes indirectly to vital indicators such as patient safety and service continuity.

Finally, the fact that the mediation is partial reveals an important insight. In other words, the relationship between job satisfaction and sustainable performance does not operate entirely through the innovation climate. There is also a direct pathway from satisfaction to performance. This finding implies that managers cannot simply rely on the innovation climate, assuming that "a positive climate automatically creates satisfaction." Instead, they must also maintain traditional human resource management (HRM) practices that directly enhance

job satisfaction such as fair compensation, equitable workload distribution, and recognition or appreciation mechanisms which remain essential for sustaining employee performance.

The findings of the study offer three key recommendations for managers and policymakers:

- Job satisfaction should be regarded as a strategic variable. The results indicate that job satisfaction is not merely a measure of employee happiness but a determinant of sustainable performance. Therefore, classic sources of job satisfaction such as pay equity, fair workload distribution, role clarity, recognition/feedback mechanisms, and career development opportunities should not be viewed separately from performance management systems. In other words, a happy employee is not a luxury but a matter of capacity management.
- Innovation climate should be seen as a tool for sustaining performance, not as a luxury comfort zone. The findings show that an innovation-supportive organizational climate helps employees maintain their performance over the long term. This is particularly critical in high-stress sectors such as healthcare, where burnout risk is high. Managers should build an environment that rewards new ideas instead of penalizing them, treats mistakes as learning opportunities, and provides adequate resources and time support. Such a climate not only fosters innovation but also enhances employee retention.
- The concept of sustainable performance should be integrated into traditional performance measurement systems. In most organizations, performance is still tracked through short-term indicators such as target achievement or task completion time. This study highlights the need to also assess the continuity dimension of performance. In healthcare institutions, this could involve periodic monitoring of indicators such as recovery capacity after shifts, perceived burnout, the ability to consistently meet work demands, and competence in organizing tasks. Indeed, this approach is becoming essential for long-term human resource planning.

As with any research, this study has certain limitations. First, the study employs a cross-sectional design, meaning that all variables were measured simultaneously. Although the direction of causality can be statistically supported, definitive causal inferences require longitudinal studies to observe changes over time. Second, the data collection method is based on self-report measures, which may introduce the risk of common method bias. Future studies could address this issue by combining self-reported data with managerial performance evaluations or other objective outcome indicators to establish multi-source data structures. Third, the research sample consists of employees working in the healthcare sector, which is characterized by high stress and critical decision-making demands. Therefore, the generalizability of the findings to other sectors (e.g., manufacturing, education, public services) may be limited. Comparative studies across different industries could reveal whether the mediating mechanism of innovation climate varies by sector. Finally, the proposed model considers only innovation climate as a mediating variable. However, the literature suggests that other factors such as burnout, psychological capital, perceived organizational support, and work engagement may also play mediating roles. Future research could test multiple mediation or moderated mediation models to gain a more nuanced understanding of these relationships.

Overall, this study fills an important gap in the literature by integrating job satisfaction, innovation climate, and sustainable performance within a unified theoretical framework. The findings indicate that job satisfaction is a strong determinant of sustainable performance, while the innovation climate functions as an organizational mechanism that partially mediates and strengthens this relationship. In conclusion, both employee satisfaction and an innovation-oriented climate should be regarded not merely as “good management practices,” but as strategic resources that enable the sustainability of performance.

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